

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ВИРТУАЛЬНАЯ РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ И ДОПОЛНЕННАЯ РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ: РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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VIRTUAL REALITY AND AUGMENTED REALITY: THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Технологии виртуальной реальности (VR) и дополненной реальности (AR) привносят революционные инновации в образовании. В то время как VR предлагает студентам полное взаимодействие в цифровой среде, AR углубляет процесс обучения, обогащая реальный мир цифровым контентом. Эти технологии предоставляют учащимся более интерактивный и увлекательный опыт обучения, помогая им лучше понимать учебные материалы и запоминать их надолго [3]. Используя VR, учащиеся могут пережить исторические события так, как если бы они были живыми на уроках истории, а с помощью AR они могут исследовать подробные трехмерные модели человеческого тела на уроках биологии. VR и AR можно использовать в различных областях, таких как виртуальные классы и лаборатории, языковое образование и профессиональное обучение [6]. Эти технологии повышают учебную мотивацию учащихся, делая учебный процесс более эффективным и способствуя равным возможностям в образовании. Эффективное использование VR и AR в образовании позволяет преподавателям делать учебные материалы более инновационными и интерактивными [5].

ABSTRACT

Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) technologies bring revolutionary innovations in education. While VR offers students full interaction in a digital environment, AR deepens the learning experience by enriching the real world with digital content. These technologies provide students with more interactive and engaging learning experiences, helping them better understand educational materials and remember them for a long time [3]. Using VR, students can experience historical events as if they were alive in history classes, while they can explore detailed three-dimensional models of the human body in biology classes through AR. VR and AR can be used in various fields such as virtual classrooms and laboratories, language education and vocational training [6]. These technologies increase students' learning motivation, making the educational process more effective and contributing to equal opportunities in education. The effective use of VR and AR in education enables teachers to make course materials more innovative and interactive [5].

Ключевые слова: Виртуальная реальность (VR), Дополненная реальность (AR), Иммерсивное обучение, Интерактивная педагогика, Образовательные технологии.

Keywords: Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Immersive Learning, Interactive Pedagogy, Educational Technology.

Entrance

Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) are among the innovative technologies that have developed rapidly recently and have significant impacts in various areas of life. While VR gives participants the chance to interact in a completely digital environment, AR is a technology that enriches the real world with digital contents and objects and presents it to users [1]. Both technologies change the user experience and offer

a wide range of applicability in various fields, from education to entertainment, healthcare to engineering [2].

The value of VR and AR in education is constantly rising with the specific learning experiences these technologies provide [3]. VR and AR offer a more interactive and interesting learning environment than classical education methods, which allows students to understand course materials more deeply and retain them in their memories for a longer time. With VR, students can experience past events and places in history classes as

if they were there, while with AR technology, they can examine three-dimensional models of the human body in detail in biology classes [2]. In addition to increasing student motivation, these innovative methods make the learning process more efficient and produce positive results in education [6].

Main Section: Uses of VR and AR Technologies in Education

Virtual Classrooms and Laboratories

VR technology allows students to attend classes and practice in virtual classrooms regardless of physical limitations. This offers a huge advantage for students who lack resources by overcoming geographical barriers. For example, risky experiments in the chemistry laboratory can be carried out safely with VR. [7]

History and Geography Lessons

VR technology makes history lessons more immersive and allows students to experience historical events as if they were there. In geography classes, students have the chance to explore various regions of the world. For example, they can visit ancient civilizations or examine natural formations in three dimensions with VR. [7]

Biology and Medical Education

AR technology offers the opportunity to examine in detail the complex structures of the human body and other living organisms in biology classes. Medical students can explore human anatomy and simulate surgical procedures thanks to AR apps. This helps them transform their theoretical knowledge into practical skills. [3] [8]

Language education

VR and AR technologies make language learning more effective. VR-based language learning applications improve students' communication skills by transporting them to virtual environments where the target language is spoken. AR applications offer the opportunity to learn vocabulary and grammar in an interactive way. [4] [7]

Vocational and Technical Education

VR and AR have wide usage areas in fields such as construction, engineering and automotive. Students can assemble machine parts, create technical drawings and work on simulations in virtual environments. This provides the opportunity to practice without expensive equipment and materials. [1] [5] [10]

VR and AR technologies offer innovative approaches in education, increasing students' motivation and making the learning process more effective [3]. These technologies have the potential to provide equal opportunities in education and facilitate access to quality education opportunities for students around the world.

Effects on Students:

1. Increased Motivation and Interest: VR and AR technologies increase students' motivation by making lessons more attractive and enjoyable [6]. With virtual reality, students have the opportunity to explore course materials and learn in an interactive way, which increases their interest in learning.

2. Better Understanding and Remembering: Visual and experiential learning can help students bet-

ter understand information and retain it in their memories for a long time [4]. For example, virtual field trips with VR or 3D model inspections powered by AR can enable them to visually see and understand abstract concepts in a concrete way.

3. Inclusivity and Accessibility: VR and AR technologies enable more students to access quality education by overcoming geographical and economic barriers [9]. Especially in regions with limited resources, virtual laboratories and classrooms make it possible for students to receive the necessary education.

4. Improved Problem Solving and Critical Thinking Skills: VR and AR applications offer students the chance to solve complex problems and improve critical thinking skills [10]. Simulations and interactive tasks strengthen students' abilities to solve problems they may encounter in real-life scenarios.

Effects on Teachers:

1. Creative Teaching Methods: VR and AR technologies offer educators the opportunity to make lessons more innovative and interactive [7]. These technologies allow teachers to diversify their lesson plans and provide students with richer and more comprehensive learning experiences.

2. Comprehensive and Interactive Course Materials: Thanks to VR and AR technologies, teachers can make course materials more comprehensive and interactive [3]. For example, a history teacher can take his students on a virtual museum tour, or a biology teacher can make his lecture more effective by using 3D models of the human body.

3. Student Tracking and Evaluation: VR and AR applications give instructors the chance to better monitor students' development and learning process [8]. Thanks to these technologies, teachers can instantly monitor student progress and make the necessary interventions in a timely manner when necessary.

4. Professional Development: VR and AR technologies support teachers' own professional development [2]. Teachers can advance their skills and teaching methods through virtual learning simulations and professional development programs.

Conclusion

VR and AR technologies carry a significant change and transformation potential in the field of education. These technologies can improve students' learning outcomes by making their learning experiences more interactive, visual, and practical. However, various obstacles must be overcome before these technologies can be used more widely in education.

First, educational institutions and administrators should allocate more resources to VR and AR technologies and actively encourage the use of these technologies in schools and universities [1]. Additionally, teachers must be provided with the necessary training and support to integrate these technologies effectively [7].

The accessibility of VR and AR technologies is also of great importance. Various resources and platforms should be created so that every student can easily access these technologies [9]. This is a vital step in ensuring equal opportunities in education.

In general, more widespread use of VR and AR technologies in education can allow students to have a

richer learning experience and increase the quality of education. For these technologies to reach their full potential, all stakeholders need to cooperate and invest in the technology in a sustainable way.

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